

Characterisation of different forms of potassium in selected soils of West Bengal

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The exchangeable as well as the non-exchangeable forms of soil potassium (K) were examined in the surface soils of an Inceptisol, an Entisol and an Alfisol of West Bengal, having contrasting properties. The non-exchangeable K in these soils was further fractionated into Step-K and Constant Rate (CR)-K by repeated extractions of these soils with boiling molar nitric acid in a sequential extraction scheme. Potassium release pattern in the given soils varied widely, thereby suggesting a wide range of K supplying capacities of these soils for crop production. Among the soils examined, the pools of water soluble, exchangeable and non-exchangeable K were the highest in the Baharampur soil (an Inceptisol), while these were the lowest in the Susunia soil, an Alfisol. The Step-K and CR-K fractions of the non-exchangeable K reserve in the present soils also exhibited similar trends. The findings are expected to be of use in suggesting potassic fertilizer application schedules for crop production in the present soils.

In soil potassium (K) is known to exist in the following forms which are present in dynamic equilibrium with each other :

The equilibrium between soluble K and exchangeable K is fast and is established within few minutes but that between exchangeable K and non-exchangeable K is much slower, requiring few days to even few weeks to establish¹.

The present study was undertaken to examine different forms of K in three surface soils (0-0.15 m) of contrasting properties and to assess therefrom the relative K supplying power of these soils for crop production.

Results and discussion

The soils of Kalyani, Baharampur and Susunia, representing the soil order of Entisol, Inceptisol and Alfisol, respectively, showed wide variations in the corresponding physico-chemical properties (Table 1). The soils from

Kalyani and Baharampur were neutral to slightly alkaline in nature, while the Susunia soil was acidic. The electrical conductivity (EC) varied from 0.08 dSm⁻¹ to 0.15 dSm⁻¹. The organic carbon content was : Kalyani > Baharampur > Susunia. Cation exchange capacity (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺) is as : Kalyani ≥ Baharampur > Susunia.

The distribution of different forms of K, namely water soluble, exchangeable and non-exchangeable K are given in Table 2. The Baharampur soil showed the highest content of all these forms of soil K, followed by the Kalyani soil. The Susunia soil had the lowest content of the given forms of soil K examined.

The step-K provides a measure of K availability from the initially non-exchangeable source while the CR-K is a measure of difficulty available K of mineral lattice sources². The release of non-exchangeable K by boiling 1M HNO₃ decreased with number of extractions. The results showed that the cumulative amount of K, released by successive extractions, was the highest in the Baharampur soil, fol-

Table 1. Important physico-chemical properties of the soils

Location of soil	Soil order	pH (1 : 25)	EC (1 : 2.5) / dSm ⁻¹	Org. C (%)	Clay (%)	CEC/ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exchangeable cation/ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	
							(Ca ²⁺ + Mg ²⁺)	Na ⁺
Kalyani	Entisol	7.5	0.12	0.60	38.7	18.4	7.5	0.57
Baharampur	Inceptisol	7.7	0.15	0.45	43.8	17.5	7.2	0.43
Susunia	Alfisol	5.9	0.08	0.26	31.3	10.3	3.9	0.30

Table 2. Different forms of potassium in soils

Location of soil	K content/[cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]		
	Water soluble	Exchangeable	Non-exchangeable
Kalyani	0.03	0.50	3.11
Baharampur	0.05	0.79	6.34
Susunia	0.02	0.30	2.14

lowed by that in the Kalyani soil (Fig. 1). A poor sequential release of K in the Susunia soil may be attributed to the predominance of kaolinitic minerals having hardly any specific site for retention of K⁺ ions in the clay fraction of the Susunia soil (an Alfisol)³. The step-K was maximum in the

Fig. 1. Cumulative extraction of potassium by boiling molar HNO₃ from soils.

first extraction in all these soils (Fig. 2), varying from 2.34 to 4.29 cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹ and gradually decreased to nil from the sixth extraction onwards. The value of CR-K ranged from 0.13 to 0.45 cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹ in the given soils. A positive correlation of step-K with non-exchangeable K content ($r = 0.90$) was obtained in the present soils. The Baharampur soil (Inceptisol), with larger K reserves and better available K status (Table 2) than the remaining two soils, may provide better K nutrition to a crop in this soil, as compared to the Susunia soil (Alfisol), which would require more frequent K fertilizer application for sustained crop production.

Experimental

Surface soils (0–0.15 m) were collected from three sites, namely Kalyani, Baharampur and Susunia, and were processed to pass through a 2-mm sieve to form the initial soil samples for the present study. The important physico-chemical properties of these soil samples, viz. pH, EC, organic carbon, clay per cent, exchangeable Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and Na⁺

Fig. 2. Step-K and Constant Rate (CR)-K of soils.

and cation exchange capacity (CEC) were determined using the standard procedures⁴. The water soluble K in the given soils was determined by using soil : water ratio of 1 : 5 as per the standard method⁵. The exchangeable K was determined by neutral normal ammonium acetate extractant in a ratio of 1 : 10 (soil : extractant)⁶. The non-exchangeable K (NEK) reserve in the given soils was determined by one-time extraction of soil with boiling molar nitric acid⁷. The NEK pools of these soils were further fractionated into step-K and CR-K fractions by resorting to the sequential extraction of the present soil samples with boiling molar nitric acid in the ratio of 1 : 10 (soil : 1 M HNO₃)⁸.

References

1. S. K. Sanyal and K. Majumder, in "Potassium in Indian Agriculture", Potash Res. Inst., India, 2001, 9.
2. O. J. Haylock, 6th Trans. *Int. Congr. Soil Sci., Paris*, 1956, 1,

Note

- 403.
3. M. Raychaudhuri and S. K. Sanyal, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 2000, **48**, 748.
 4. C. S. Piper, "Soil and Plant Analysis", University of Adelaide, Adelaide, 1950; M. L. Jackson, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi, 1967.
 5. J. S. Grewal and J. S. Kanwar, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1966, **14**, 63.
 6. P. F. Pratt, in "Methods of Soil Analysis, Part 2", ed. C. A. Black, *Agron.* 9, Madison, Wisconsin, 1965, 1019.
 7. D. Knudsen, G. A. Peterson and P. F. Pratt, in "Methods of Soil Analysis, Part 2", ed. Page, *Agron.* 9, 1982, 225.
 8. A. J. MacLean, *Can. J. Soil Sci.*, 1961, **41**, 196.